

IMPACT OF SECTORAL FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: 2010Q1-2023Q4

Utenge Monday Udoinyang, Ogwuche David D., And Ologunla Sunday Emmanuel

Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences, Bingham University, Karu, Nigeria

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Abstract: *Foreign direct investment (FDI) is a crucial source of investment in developing countries. As sector-wise decomposed FDI has a bearing on the economic growth process. However, sectoral FDI cannot exert equal impact on growth. This is due to the fact that, each of these sectors are having different investment absorption capacity, technological base and even regulatory framework etc. Thus, this paper investigated the impact of sectoral foreign direct investment on growth in Nigeria from 2010Q1 to 2023Q4 using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Regression technique. Results revealed agriculture FDI; services FDI; and telecommunication FDI are the main significant short-run drivers of economic growth in Nigeria during this study period. While only telecommunication FDI appears to drive output growth significantly in the long-run in Nigeria. On a basis of variable-by-variable analysis, this paper found that one period lagged agriculture FDI is positively and significantly related to growth in the short-run. On the other hand, over the long term, the projected impact of agriculture FDI on growth is statistically insignificant and negative. While, the findings indicated that manufacturing FDI appears to affect growth negatively both in the short-run and long run. Furthermore, the estimated impact of services FDI at level on growth is positive and significant in the short run. Similarly, services FDI is insignificant and positively related to growth in the long run. Also, the coefficient of telecommunication FDI is negative and significant both in the short run and long run. Therefore, this research recommended that the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment and the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development should encourage value addition by promoting agro-processing industries to reduce dependence on raw exports, given the positive short-run and negative long-run impact of agriculture FDI. Since manufacturing FDI negatively impacts growth in both short and long run, Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment and in active collaboration with Manufacturers Association of Nigeria should make concrete efforts to address structural bottlenecks such as high production costs, inadequate power supply, and poor logistics in the manufacturing sub sector. Further, the Nigerian Communications Commission should put in place stronger regulatory oversight to ensure fair pricing, quality service, and increased competition given the negative impact of telecommunications FDI on*

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growth. Also, since services FDI has a positive short-run and weak long-run impact on growth, the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission should strive to ensure a business-friendly regulatory environment that attracts long-term investments in high-value services.

I. Introduction

Globally, economic growth is the goal of any nation's economy (World Bank [WB], 2021). In order to maintain high economic growth, a sustainable amount of saving and investment (Sredojevic et al., 2016), technical progress (Solow, 1956), human capital accumulation, and research and development (R&D) investment (Grossman & Helpman, 1991; Romer, 1990), as well as global economic integration (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development [UNCTAD], 2018), are needed. Unfortunately, most developing countries such as Nigeria continue to suffer from the vicious circle of underdevelopment – low productivity leads to low income; this in turn leads to low savings; low savings leads to low investment; and low investment leads to low productivity (Masoud, 2014; Welteji, 2018; United Nations [UN], 2020).

In addition, developing countries are home to many poor people in the world. For example, about 1.3 billion people, or 22% of the world's population, live in multidimensional poverty in 107 developing countries (World Vision, 2022). For example, 133 million Nigerians lives multidimensional poverty (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). Nigeria's GDP growth has been volatile, with periods of rapid expansion followed by downturns, largely driven by fluctuations in

oil prices (World Bank, 2020). Despite being an oil-rich nation, Nigeria faces structural challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, weak institutions, and high levels of poverty. Efforts to diversify the economy away from oil dependence and promote sectors such as agriculture and manufacturing are underway, but progress has been slow. Additionally, socio-political factors such as corruption and insecurity pose significant obstacles to sustained economic growth and development in Nigeria. Therefore, Nigeria needs rapid economic growth to free its citizens from poverty and ensure sustainable development. Hence, Nigeria require foreign resources, such as foreign direct investment (FDI), to break vicious circle of underdevelopment and to sustain economic growth. It is the most stable and essential foreign source of financing, accounting for 39% of total incoming capital in developing economies (UNCTAD, 2018). By complementing local savings, injecting additional capital, and providing more effective management, marketing, and technology, FDI can break the vicious circle of underdevelopment and induce fast economic growth (Herzer, 2012). By utilising cheap labour, which has zero or very low marginal products, it fuels the economic growth of developing countries (Ali & Asgher, 2016). Additionally, it improves economic growth and

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promotes health and education throughout society by ensuring an equitable distribution of income through increased use of unskilled labour, tax payments, and lower production prices (Carp, 2012). By increasing manufacturing exports, it also stimulates economic growth (McMillan et al., 2017). The experiences of Asian Tiger countries (Taiwan, South Korea, Singapore, and Hong Kong) also demonstrate that they achieved significant economic progress with substantial infusions of FDI (Chaudhury et al., 2020).

Meanwhile, the empirical evidence on FDI-growth is mixed. For example, Agrawal (2015), Ezeji et al. (2015), Fatmawati et al. (2018), Olagbaju and Akinlo (2018), and Dinh et al. (2019) are only a few examples of studies that support the prevalent belief that FDI drives economic growth. While scholars such as Falki (2009), Ludosean (2012), Hossain and Mahammed (2011), Saqib et al. (2013), Herzer (2012), Awe (2013), Edrees (2015), and Mohamed and Isak (2017) suggest that it has a detrimental effect on the economic progress of the host country. Profit repatriation, exploitation of natural resources and labour, and monopolistic competition all contribute to this phenomenon. While, Belloumi (2014), Aga (2014), Ocaya et al. (2013), and Ray (2012) disagree with the previous two arguments and claiming that FDI has a negligible effect on economic growth.

Additionally, most of the FDI-growth analyses have been at the aggregate levels. The limited

empirical evidence on the growth impacts of sectoral FDI is much more in the developing world such as Nigeria. However, sector-wise decomposed FDI has a bearing on the impact it would exert on the economic growth process. For example, FDI cannot exert equal economic influences in all the sectors of an economy. This is due to the fact that, each of these sectors are having different investment absorption capacity, technological base and even regulatory framework etc. (Li & Liu, 2005; and Alfaro, 2003). Further, not all sectors can absorb foreign capital and technology equally or create links with each other. For example, FDI in the primary sector is often in the form of megaprojects that involve massive capital flows, resulting in increased rent-seeking and reduced competition (Ali & Asgher, 2016). Thus, this paper examined the impact of sectoral foreign direct investment on economic growth in Nigeria, focusing on agricultural, manufacturing, services and telecommunication sectors from 2010Q1 to 2023Q4 using quarterly time series data.

The following research questions guided the research:

- i. How foreign direct investment does flows to agriculture impact on economic growth in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the impact of foreign direct investment flows to manufacturing on economic growth in Nigeria?
- iii. To what extent does foreign direct investment flows to service sector affect economic growth in Nigeria?

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iv. iv. What impact does foreign direct investment flows to telecommunication have on economic growth in Nigeria?

II. Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Foreign direct investment

The term FDI involve the process of bringing in investors resources (money, material and man) from foreign countries into the local economy for productive purposes. FDI is a foreign investment made so as to acquire a lasting management interest (for instance, 10% of voting stocks) and at least 10% of equity shares in an enterprise operating in another country other than that of investors' country (Danja, 2012). FDI is the direct transfer of technological know-how and managerial practices to the host country. Typically, FDI can take the form of establishing a new enterprise (Greenfield investment) or acquiring an existing business (mergers and acquisitions). The primary goal of FDI is to establish a controlling interest, which is generally achieved by acquiring at least 10% of the voting shares in a foreign entity (OECD, 2024).

Economic growth

The rise in an economy's production of goods and services over a given time frame is referred to as output growth. This paper measured economic growth using real gross domestic product growth rate, as the most popular metric for measuring output in the literature. Real GDP growth rate, after accounting for inflation, is the entire amount of goods and services generated in an

economy at constant prices. Real gross domestic product is a macroeconomic measure of the value of economic output adjusted for price changes. This adjustment transforms the money-value measure, nominal GDP, into an index for the quantity of total output (Ologbenla, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical background of this paper is the growth accounting equation derived from the Solow growth model. The Solow model in particular represented the seminal contribution to the neoclassical theory of growth and later earned Robert Solow the Noble Prize in economics. It expanded on the Harrod-Dormar formulation by adding a second factor, labour, and introducing a third independent variable, technology, to the growth equation. Unlike the fixed-coefficient, constant-returns to scale assumption of the Harrod-Dormar model, Solow's neoclassical growth model exhibited diminishing returns to labour and capital separately and constant returns to both factors jointly. Technological progress became the residual factor explaining long-term growth, and its level was assumed to be exogenously determined, that is, independently of all other factors. More formally, the Solow neoclassical growth model uses a standard aggregate production function in which

$$Y = K^{\alpha}(AL)^{1 - \alpha} \quad (1)$$

Where Y is the gross domestic product, K is the stock of capital (which may include human capital as well as physical capital), L is labour, and A represents productivity of labour, which

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grows at an exogenous rate. For developed countries, this rate has been estimated at about 2% per year. It may be smaller or larger in developing countries, depending on whether they are stagnating or catching up with the developed countries. Because the rate of technological progress is given exogenously (at 2% per year), the Solow neoclassical model is sometimes called an “exogenous growth model. In equation (1), α represents the elasticity of output with respect to capital (the percentage increase in GDP resulting from a 1% increase in human and physical capital). The physical capital component is usually measured statistically as the share of capital in a country’s national income accounts. Since α is assumed to be less than 1 and private capital is assumed to be paid its marginal product so that there are no external economies, this formulation of neoclassical growth theory yields diminishing returns to both capital and to labour.

In the growth accounting equation, output grows because of increases in inputs as well as increases in productivity, as a result of improved technology and a highly skilled labour force. Thus, the production function presents a quantitative connection between inputs and output as follows:

$$Y = Af(K, L) \quad (2)$$

Where Y is output growth, K is capital, L is labour and A is total factor productivity. To begin with, the capital stock is assumed to consist of two components: domestic and foreign- owned

capital stock. Therefore, for the model specification, capital is represented by sectoral foreign direct investment. The dependent variable for the model is economic growth which will be measured by real gross domestic product growth rate, as the most widely used indicator for output growth. While the independent variables for the model are sectoral foreign direct investment flows to agriculture, manufacturing, services and telecommunication sectors.

Empirical Review

Using the Ordinary Least Squares regression methodology, Ozili (2025) examined the effect of foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows on economic growth in Nigeria from 2010 to 2019. Findings revealed that foreign direct investment inflows do not have a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Meanwhile, population size, real interest rate, domestic private credit and the inflation rate are significant determinants of economic growth in Nigeria while gross capital formation is an insignificant determinant of economic growth in Nigeria. The implication of the findings is that policy makers in Nigeria should focus on other drivers of economic growth other than foreign direct investment inflows when developing policy initiatives to stimulate economic growth in Nigeria.

Using annual time series data from 1985 to 2019, Mathebula et al. (2024) examined the effect of foreign direct investment on South Africa's economic growth using Autoregressive Lag Distribution method. The results showed a

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negative long-run relationship between FDI and economic growth, while saving rate positively correlated with growth. Inflation and real interest rate also had negative long-run relationships. The study recommended that the government should implement strategies to attract foreign investment, amongst others.

Yangailo (2024) examined the long-term relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI), gross national income (GNI) per capita, exports and economic growth in Zambia from 1994 to 2023. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) results showed that while FDI contributes positively to economic growth, GNI per capita and exports have a more significant impact. The study highlights the need for Zambia to strengthen its institutional framework, improve infrastructure and invest in human capital to sustain FDI inflows and reduce economic vulnerabilities.

Using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Panel regression, Despotović et al. (2024) examined the effects of sectoral structure of foreign direct investment on economic development in European developing countries. Study results revealed that primary and secondary sectors FDI in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) and the Western Balkans (WBs), which are still predominantly labor-intensive have a negative impact on economic development. As opposed to the agricultural and industrial sectors, the services, under the influence of technological progress, is profiled as a capital-intensive sector with a statistically significant

positive impact on economic growth and development. The study recommended reformulation of WBs industrial policy that will be based on export-oriented reindustrialization, as well as the identification of propulsive industrial branches and the providing incentives to domestic companies.

Fazaalloh (2024) analyzed the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI) on economic growth employing sectoral data at the provincial level (33 provinces) in Indonesia over 2010–2019. Based on the fixed effects estimator, the study estimation results proved that, in general, FDI significantly positively impacts economic growth in the Indonesian provinces. The study also found that FDI in the mining, manufacturing, water, gas and electricity, hotels and restaurants, and real estate sectors has a significant positive effect on economic growth. Meanwhile, only FDI in the agricultural sector has a significant negative impact. Further, estimation results confirmed that FDI in the manufacturing sector contributes positively and has a considerable impact. The study recommended that the government should sort out which sectoral FDI stimulates economic growth. Since not all FDI sectors are direct drivers of economic growth.

Using Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS), Akindipe (2023) examined the effect of sectoral FDI on Nigeria's economic growth between 1981 and 2020. Findings from the DOLS showed that all the sectoral FDIs apart from services and mining and quarrying, had statistically significantly positive effects on economic growth.

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Lack of backward linkages accounted for the negative effect of service FDI on growth and the statistically insignificant positive effect of mining and quarrying was as a result of little linkage between the sector and the rest of the economy. The government should, therefore, encourage domestic industry by creating economic linkages and build local capacity to absorb new innovation brought by the foreign investors to the country.

Emako et al. (2022) analyzed the effect of sector-specific foreign direct investment (FDI) (the primary, secondary, and tertiary sectors) on economic growth in 19 developing countries over the period 2005–2018. A robust Two-Step System Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) was utilised for the analysis of the data. The study found that FDI's growth effect is indeed influenced by its sectoral composition in developing countries. The finding revealed that FDI in manufacturing has a positive and statistically significant influence on economic growth, whereas FDI in the tertiary sector has a statistically significant negative effect on economic growth, but FDI in the primary sector has a negative but negligible effect on economic growth. Further, the study concluded from the above results that the more manufacturing FDI that countries attract, the greater their economic growth will be. In light of this, the countries should provide special incentives like tariff reductions, tax holidays, and cheap-rented land supplies in order to attract more manufacturing sector FDI.

Opoku et al. (2019) re-examined the impact of FDI on economic growth in Africa using the system generalized method of moments. The results revealed that, while FDI positively and unconditionally spurs economic growth, its growth-enhancing effect is imaginary when the conditional sectoral effects are introduced. On the channels of manifestation, the study noticed that the pass-through impact of FDI is only significant for the agricultural and service sectors. The study documented two important implications for policy in relation to the direct and indirect impact of FDI. First, without the indirect effect, FDI directly and significantly contributes to economic growth in Africa. The direct effect can be related to FDI's role in stimulating the region's domestic savings as well as spurring technological progress in addition to increasing the multiplicity of goods and services. Second, FDI significantly improves growth in economies with well-developed agricultural and service sectors.

Applying a time-varying parameter model with vector autoregressive specification, Jana et al. (2019) examined how sector-wise FDI inflows can affect the growth of respective sectors in the context of an emerging economy like India. The study used a number of econometric tests, such as Johansen's cointegration test, vector error correction model, Granger causality test, variance decomposition analysis and impulse response analysis, to arrive at robust results. The study found inward FDI to be non-contributive to the agricultural output growth. However, a

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reverse causality is found wherein agricultural output is found to be attracting more FDI into the sector. It also documents interesting evidence for manufacturing sector where the FDI inflow is found to affect its output positively for a couple of years. Regarding service sector, the study confirmed a bidirectional causality between FDI and growth both for the short and long run. On the basis of the findings, the study suggested economic policymakers to rejuvenate the primary sector of India so that it can attract and absorb more FDI and ensure sustainable economic growth.

Using a model based on a modified neoclassical production function, in which FDI is viewed as an input in the production process, Akanegbu and Chizea (2017) investigated the hypothesis of whether or not FDI has a positive and significant impact on output growth in the Nigerian economy. The study employed unit root test and Granger-Causality test. The results of the estimation analysis obtained revealed that there exists a positive relationship between FDI and output growth in the Nigerian economy. The study recommended that the policies that will increase FDI should be encouraged.

The impact of foreign direct investment on Nigeria's manufacturing industry was evaluated by Ekienabor et al. (2016). The Ordinary Least

$$GDP_{pc} = \alpha + \beta_1 FDI + \beta_2 GCI + \beta_3 EXP + \beta_4 EU + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

Where, FDI is further decomposed into sectoral foreign direct investment flows to agricultural, industry, and service sectors; GCI = Global

Squares econometric regression model was used to assess the correlation between foreign direct investments and key economic indicators such interest rates, industrial output, and currency rates. The model revealed a positive relationship between foreign direct investment and each of the variables (manufacturing output, exchange rate and interest rate). The study recommended that government should step up efforts in attracting foreign direct investment into the sector by ensuring that investor confidence is protected.

III. Data and Method

In this paper, the selected research design is the ex-post facto design. The ex-post facto design is particularly suited for studies aiming to decipher statistical associations between dependent and independent variables, primarily to establish cause-and-effect relationships.

Model Specification

This paper empirical model specification follows the theoretical framework and model that was adapted from the work of Despotović et al. (2024) that examined the effects of sectoral structure of foreign direct investment on economic development in European developing countries, using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Panel regression from 2011 to 2019. The model applied in the study is of the form:

competitive index; EXP = Export; EU = European Union (EU) members Vs candidates for EU membership. However, the model of

Despotović et al. (2024) was modified by including sectoral foreign direct investment flows to agriculture, manufacturing, services,

$$RGDPG_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AGFDI_t + \beta_2 MAFDI_t + \beta_3 SEFDI_t + \beta_4 TEFDI_{tt} + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

Where, RGDPG = Real gross domestic product growth rate; AGFDI = Agriculture FDI; MAFDI = Manufacturing FDI; SEFDI = Services FDI; and TEFDI = Telecommunication FDI. β_0 = The intercept or autonomous parameter estimate, β_1 to β_4 = Parameter estimate representing the coefficient of AGFDI, MAFDI, SEFDI, and TEFDI respectively, and ε_t - other variables not explicitly included in the model. The apriori'

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \partial_j \Delta X_{t-j} + \phi_1 y_{t-1} + \phi_2 X_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad (5)$$

Where Δ denotes the first difference operator, β_i , ∂_j stand for the short-run coefficients, ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 are for the long-run coefficients and μ_t is the

$$\Delta RGDPG_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_{1i} RGDPG_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_{2j} \Delta AGFDI_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^o \alpha_{3k} \Delta MAFDI_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^p \alpha_{4l} \Delta SEFDI_{t-l} + \sum_{i=0}^r \alpha_{5i} \Delta TEFDI_{t-i} + \alpha_6 RGDPG_{t-1} + \alpha_7 AGFDI_{t-1} + \alpha_8 MAFDI_{t-1} + \alpha_9 SEFDI_{t-1} + \alpha_{10} TEFDI_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (6)$$

The bounds test is conducted by testing the null hypothesis (H_0) against the alternative hypothesis (H_1) using the following equations:

$$H_0 : \alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = \alpha_4 = \alpha_5 = 0 \text{ And } H_1 : \alpha_1 \neq \alpha_2 \neq \alpha_3 \neq \alpha_4 \neq \alpha_5 \neq 0$$

The results of the bounds test derived from the computed F-Statistic are comparable to those of Pesaran et al. (2001), who concluded that cointegration between the series is present if the

and telecommunication sectors. Thus, the modified model is presented as follows:

expectations are determined by the principles of economic theory and refer to the expected relationship between the explained variable and the explanatory variable(s). It is expected that $\beta_1 - \beta_4 > 0$. The paper used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) framework introduced by Pesaran et al. (2001). The ARDL model is specified as follows to run the bound test for cointegration:

disturbance(white noise) term. Transforming equation (4) into an ARDL Model results as follows:

F-Statistic is greater than the upper bound I (1) in each case, rejecting the null hypothesis of no cointegration.

Mathematically, the series Error Correction Model with the ARDL framework is as follows:

$$\Delta RGDPG_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_{1i} \Delta RGDPG_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_{2j} \Delta AGFDI_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^o \alpha_{3k} \Delta MAFDI_{t-k} + \sum_{l=0}^p \alpha_{4l} \Delta SEFDI_{t-l} + \sum_{l=0}^q \alpha_{5l} \Delta TEFDI_{t-l} + ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \text{-----(7)}$$

Where,

ECT_{t-1} = lagged Error correction term. The output evolution process that agents use to react to the prior period of prediction errors is captured by the ECT.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique has an added advantage in the sense that it can be applied for any order of integration due to its dynamic nature. The ARDL method as suggested by Pesaran et al. (2001) can be adopted regardless of the integration order of the

independent variables whether they are purely I (0), purely I (1) or mutually co-integrated (Gökmenoğlu & Taspınar, 2016; Katircioğlu, 2009, 2010). The ARDL framework gives efficient results because it is free from serial correlation and endogeneity problems and can be estimated in the presence of endogenous explanatory Variables (Pesaran et al., 2001). The ARDL technique give more robust results for a small sample size than other conventional co-integration model

IV. Results and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the paper.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	RGDP	AGFDI	MAFDI	SEFDI	TEFDI
Mean	3.092462	34.01304	164.8841	175.2889	133.9857
Maximum	8.005656	197.8500	605.0400	817.3800	884.8500
Minimum	-1.794250	0.100000	3.560000	1.200000	0.340000
Std. Dev.	2.458080	41.81637	152.0828	184.1754	193.1535
Skewness	-0.068282	1.815913	1.243471	1.545038	2.297331
Kurtosis	2.206443	6.449026	3.784905	5.130448	7.991303
Jarque-Bera	1.512892	58.53384	15.86890	32.87056	107.3894
Probability	0.469331	0.000000	0.000358	0.000000	0.000000
Observations	56	56	56	56	56

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025 (Eviews-12)

From Table 2, Real Gross Domestic Product Growth Rate (RGDP) has an approximate

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average of 3.092% and it ranges from -1.794250 (minimum) to 8.005656 (maximum), with a standard deviation of 2.458%. While, Agriculture FDI (AGFDI) has a mean value of 34.013 percent, with the standard deviation of 41.816%, minimum and maximum values of 0.100000 and 197.8500 respectively. Similarly, Manufacturing FDI (MAFDI) has an approximate average of 164.884% and it ranges from 3.560000 (minimum) to 605.0400 (maximum), with a standard deviation of 152.083 percent. Also, Services FDI (SEFDI) has an approximate average of 175.289 % and it ranges from 1.200000 (minimum) to 817.3800 (maximum), with a standard deviation of 184.175%. Further, Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI), has an approximate average of 133.986 percent and it ranges from 0.340000 (minimum) to 884.8500 (maximum), with a standard deviation of 193.154 percent.

Furthermore, Table 2 displayed the skewness coefficient, a measure of how far a distribution deviates from symmetry, with all the variables

Table 3: Correlation Matrix Result

	RGDP	AGFDI	MAFDI	SEFDI	TEFDI
RGDP	1				
AGFDI	-0.345213	1			
MAFDI	0.087611	0.032309	1		
SEFDI	-0.284809	0.467960	0.003807	1	
TEFDI	-0.054183	-0.073473	-0.078840	-0.094357	1

Source: Researcher’s Computation Using EViews-12 (2024)

having skewness values greater than one, except RGDP variable with skewness value less than one. The entire data series are not platykurtic (not having negative values), as confirmed by the kurtosis result, which measures a distribution's degree of peakedness in relation to a normal distribution. Additionally, as evidenced by the probability values of each variable's corresponding Jarque-Bera statistics, except for RGDP variable, the variables are not nominally distributed. Since the accompanying Jarque-Bera probability values of these variables have a significance level less than 5%, it may be concluded that they don't have a normal distribution.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis provides the valuable insights into how each of the independent variables relates to the dependent variable. The correlation coefficients in this analysis help to identify whether these variables move together in a positive or negative direction and the strength of these relationships.

The correlation coefficients presented in Table 3 are considerably below 0.8, indicating that there is no serious multi-collinearity in the model. By

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implications, all the variables are free from the problem of multicollinearity. Additionally, the correlation coefficients presented in Table 3 indicated a negative association amongst real gross domestic product growth rate (RGDP) and sectoral FDI inflows from agriculture, services and telecommunication in Nigeria. While, the correlation between RGDP and Manufacturing FDI was positive. Further, the correlation between RGDP and Manufacturing FDI was found to be the strongest at 34%.

Table 4 Traditional Unit Root Test Results (Trend and Intercept)

Variable	Method	Level Stat. (Prob.)	First Diff. Stat. (Prob.)	Order of Integration
RGDP	ADF	-2.800089 (0.2036)	-3.036175**(0.0378)	I(1)
AGFDI	ADF	-4.139141** (0.0099)	-7.451474*(0.0000)	I(0)
MAFDI	ADF	-5.676490*(0.0000)	-8.335331*(0.0000)	I(0)
SEFDI	ADF	-5.606607*(0.0001)	-10.32899*(0.0000)	I(0)
TEFDI	ADF	-7.117746*(0.0000)	-8.432498*(0.0000)	I(0)

Note: *, ** Indicates stationary at the 1% and 5% level.

Source: Researcher’s Computations using E-Views 12

Agriculture FDI (AGFDI); Manufacturing FDI (MAFDI); Services FDI (SEFDI); and Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) variables tends to be stationary at level. However, Real GDP growth rates (RGDP) variable is likely to be stationary in first difference.

Co-integration Results

The variables were all found to be integrated at different orders; hence, they all satisfied the

Unit Root Results

A unit root test, such as the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, is a common statistical method used to determine whether a time series data set is stationary. The ADF test checks for a unit root in a time series by testing the null hypothesis that the series has a unit root (non-stationary) against the alternative hypothesis that the series is stationary. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test results are displayed in Table 4 as follows:

ARDL-bound testing approach which necessitates every variable in the equation to be static either at level or at first difference or modification. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root results presented in Table 3, implies that the bounds testing approach is applicable in this investigation, as all the variables are a mixture of I(1) and I(0). The co-integration test helps to establish the existence of long run equilibrium relationships among variables of interest. If co-integration is found among variables, ARDL error correction model

becomes applicable. The result of the cointegration test is presented in Table 5:

Table 5: Result of ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationships Exist		
Test Statistic	Value	K
F-Statistic	4.116069	4
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
5%	2.56	3.49

Source: Researcher’s Computations based on E-Views 12

From Table 5, the bounds test value of the F-statistics which is 4.116069 is higher than the values of the upper and lower bound limit which are 2.56 and 3.49 at 5% critical level of significance. This means that there is a long run equilibrium relationship between the dependent

variable and the explanatory variables of the model. In light of the cointegration of the dependent variable with the regressors, the paper proceeded to estimates the error correction and the long-term models. Table 6 presented the outcomes of the estimates as follows:

Table 6: ARDL Regression Results

Dependent Variable: D (RGDP)

Co-integrating Estimates (ECM Estimates)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(AGFDI)	-0.003489	0.002960	-1.178608	0.2478
D(AGFDI(-1))	0.006324	0.002673	2.365815	0.0246
D(AGFDI(-2))	0.001389	0.002603	0.533706	0.5975
D(MAFDI)	-0.000697	0.000615	-1.133472	0.2660
D(MAFDI(-1))	6.420005	0.000736	0.087206	0.9311
D(MAFDI(-2))	-0.000373	0.000655	-0.569319	0.5734
D(SEFDI)	0.001382	0.000576	2.397412	0.0229
D(SEFDI(-1))	-9.500005	0.000702	-0.135296	0.8933
D(SEFDI(-2))	0.000469	0.000707	0.663273	0.5122
D(TEFDI)	-0.000837	0.000394	-2.126151	0.0418
D(TEFDI(-1))	0.002505	0.000689	3.635848	0.0010

D(TEFDI(-2))	0.001407	0.000616	2.284025	0.0296
CointEq(-1)*	-0.101580	0.018924	-5.367720	0.0000
R-squared	0.585981			
Adjusted R-squared	0.396715			
Durbin-Watson stat	1.012809			
Long Run				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
AGFDI	-0.113384	0.062244	-1.821622	0.0785
MAFDI	-0.024774	0.018308	-1.353191	0.1861
SEFDI	0.023864	0.016372	1.457613	0.1553
TEFDI	-0.036263	0.015643	-2.318220	0.0274
C	10.99014	4.148470	2.649203	0.0127

Source: Researcher’s Computation Using EViews-12 (2025)

Based on Table 6, Agriculture FDI (AGFDI); Services FDI (SEFDI); and Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) variables employed in this investigation has a statistically significant impact on economic growth in the short-run. While, only Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) variable that has a statistically significant long-run impact on growth. The estimated ARDL regression result indicated that Agriculture FDI (AGFDI); Services FDI (SEFDI); and Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) are the main significant short-run drivers of economic growth in Nigeria during the period of investigation. While only Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) appears to drive economic growth significantly in the long-run in Nigeria.

Furthermore, one period lagged Agriculture FDI (AGFDI); Manufacturing FDI (MAFDI), Services FDI (SEFDI) at level; and

Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) are in agreement with this paper apriori expectations. While, Services FDI (SEFDI) align with this paper apriori expectations in the long run. However, Agriculture FDI (AGFDI); Manufacturing FDI (MAFDI), and Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) are not conformity with this paper apriori expectations in in the long run. Overall, the analysis's findings are consistent with those of Akindipe (2023), and Emako et al. (2022) who have all demonstrated that FDI’s growth impact is influenced by its sectoral composition such as agriculture, manufacturing, services and communications. At the one percent level, the Error Correction Model is highly statistically significant, negatively signed, and as expected. This provides more proof that the dependent variable and the regressors have a long-run relationship. The coefficient's absolute value, which falls between 0 and 1, shows that, in order to keep the

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equilibrium, yearly corrections are made to the short-run divergence from the equilibrium (long-run) position, which is roughly 10%. Since the explanatory variables account for more than 59% of the variation in economic growth, the model appears to be well-fitting, as indicated by the R-squared value of 0.585981. On the other hand, the DW figure of 1.012809 indicated that

there is no problem with serial correlation. As such, the conclusions of this study can be trusted for developing policy recommendations.

Post-Estimation Test Results

The paper conducted a few diagnostic tests to assess the model's stability and applicability as well as the validity of the results. Results is as presented in Table 7 as follows:

Table 7: Diagnostic Test Results

Test	Null Hypothesis	T-Statistic	Prob
Jarque-Bera	There is a normal distribution	1.993	0.37
Heteroskedasticity: LM	No conditional heteroscedasticity	1.299	0.26
Heteroskedasticity: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	No conditional heteroscedasticity	0.624	0.86

Source: Researcher's Computations based on E-Views 12

From Table 7, the model did not display serial correlation or heteroskedasticity during the study period. The heteroscedasticity tests indicated that the residuals are homoscedastic. The results of the diagnostic tests for serial correlation and heteroscedasticity suggested that the data is reasonably well behaved. Furthermore, the p-value for the normality test for the research period is greater than 0.05, indicating that the residues are distributed normally. This results in a uniform distribution

of the residuals. As a result, the normal distribution null hypothesis was not rejected.

4.5.1 Stability Test Result

The stability test in Figure 1 also revealed that the output growth model is stable during the study period as the plots of the charts lie within the critical bounds at 5% significant level. Bahmani-Oskooee and Rehman, (2005) noted that the null hypothesis that states the regression equation is correctly specified cannot be rejected when the plot of these statistics are within the critical boundaries at 5% significant level

Figure 4.1: Stability Tests Result

Source: Researcher's Plot using E-Views 12

Discussion of Findings

From the estimated ARDL regression results in Table 6, Agriculture FDI (AGFDI); Services FDI (SEFDI); and Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) variables has a statistically significant impact on economic growth in the short-run. While, only Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) variable that has a statistically significant long-run impact on growth. The estimated ARDL regression result indicated that Agriculture FDI (AGFDI); Services FDI (SEFDI); and Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) are the main significant short-run drivers of economic growth in Nigeria during the period under review. While only Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) appears to drive economic growth significantly in the long-run in Nigeria.

On a basis of variable-by-variable analysis, this paper found that one period lagged agriculture FDI is positively and significantly related to growth in the short-run. Consequently, one percentage increase in one period lagged

agriculture FDI will lead to an increase in growth in Nigeria by 0.06 percent in the short run. This outcome is consistent with the a priori expectations of this investigation and prior studies such as Emako et al. (2022) and Akindipe (2023) who all reported that FDI's growth effect is influenced by its sectoral composition and sectoral FDIs apart from services and mining and quarrying, had statistically significantly positive effects on economic growth. On the other hand, over the long term, the projected impact of agriculture FDI on economic growth is statistically insignificant and negative. Specifically, one percentage increase in agriculture FDI will lead to a decrease in economic growth by -0.11% in the long-run. This outcome is line with Despotović et al. (2024) and Mathebula et al. (2024) that found that primary FDI such as agriculture has a negative impact on growth.

On the other hand, the findings indicated that manufacturing FDI appears to affect economic growth negatively in the short-run. Controlling for other factors, for instance, a 1 percent

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increase in manufacturing FDI will lead to a decrease in growth by -0.07% in the short run. This outcome is inconsistent with the a priori expectations of the research and an indication that manufacturing FDI is not a significant drive of output growth in the short-run. Similarly, manufacturing FDI appears to affect growth insignificantly and negatively in the long run. Specifically, one percentage increase in manufacturing FDI will lead to a decrease in growth by approximately -0.02% in the long-run. This outcome is inconsistent with the investigation of Akindipe (2023), Fazaalloh (2024) and Jana et al. (2019) whose findings confirmed that FDI in the manufacturing sector contributes positively and has a considerable impact on growth.

Furthermore, the estimated impact of services FDI at level on economic growth is positive and significant in the short run. By implication, one percentage change or increase in services FDI at level will lead to 0.01% increase in economic growth in the short-run. This outcome is consistent with the a priori expectations of this investigation, as services FDI is expected to be directly related to output growth. Similarly, services FDI is insignificant and positively related to economic growth in the long run. Specifically, one percentage increase in services FDI rise will lead to an increase in economic growth by approximately 0.02% in the long-run. This finding is in agreement with Opoku et al. (2019) who re-examined the impact of FDI on

economic growth in Africa noticed that the pass-through impact of FDI is only significant for the agricultural and service sectors.

The coefficient of telecommunication FDI is negative and significant both in the short run and long run. Consequently, if there is a 1% increase in telecommunication FDI it is predicted that there may be a decrease of -0.08% and -0.04% in economic growth in Nigeria both in the short run and long run. This outcome is inconsistent with the a priori expectations of this research. Further, this outcome is consistent with Akindipe (2023) who found that all the sectoral FDIs apart from services and mining and quarrying, had statistically significantly positive effects on economic growth.

V. Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper investigated the impact of sectoral foreign direct investment on economic growth in Nigeria from 2010Q1 to 2023Q4 using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Regression technique. Results revealed that Agriculture FDI (AGFDI); Services FDI (SEFDI); and Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) are the main significant short-run drivers of economic growth in Nigeria during the period under investigation. While only Telecommunication FDI (TEFDI) appears to drive economic growth significantly in the long-run in Nigeria.

On a basis of variable-by-variable analysis, this research found that one period lagged agriculture FDI is positively and significantly related to growth in the short-run. On the other

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hand, over the long term, the projected impact of agriculture FDI on growth is statistically insignificant and negative. While, the findings indicated that manufacturing FDI affected economic growth negatively both in the short-run and long run. Furthermore, the estimated impact of services FDI at level on growth is positive and significant in the short run. Similarly, services FDI is insignificant and positively related to economic growth in the long run. Also, the coefficient of telecommunication FDI is negative and significant both in the short run and long run. Therefore, the following recommendations were raised from the research findings.

i. Given the positive short-run and negative long-run impact of agriculture FDI on growth, the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI) and the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) should encourage value addition by promoting agro-processing industries to reduce dependence on raw exports.

ii. Since manufacturing FDI negatively impacts growth in both short and long run, Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment (FMITI) and in active collaboration with Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN) should make concrete efforts to address structural bottlenecks such as high production costs, inadequate power supply, and poor logistics in the manufacturing sub sector.

iii. The negative impact of telecommunications FDI on growth suggests inefficiencies that must be addressed. Thus, the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) should put in place stronger regulatory oversight to ensure fair pricing, quality service, and increased competition.

iv. Since services FDI has a positive short-run and weak long-run impact on growth, the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC) should strive to ensure a business-friendly regulatory environment that attracts long-term investments in high-value services.

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